

The Impact of Belt and Road Initiative on Tourism Industry around Asian Countries

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Abstract: More than 60 countries and 4.4 billion people – one-third of global economic output, 40% of global trade, and more than 60% of the world's population – make the BRI a cultural route with access to the world's top tourist resources, including 80% of global cultural heritage. BRI links popular tourism destinations. COVID-19 shook China's economy two months ago. The closure harmed tourism. OBOR's impact on Asian tourism will be examined. We lack economic data to examine covid-19 this year. We'll prioritize One Belt, One Road. This study explores Asian tourism and OBOR. This year's covid-19 research requires economic data. Even if the Belt and Road nations are part of a low-end and poor tourist value chain with inadequate infrastructure, unprofessional tourism practitioners, and low service standards, policy help and political collaboration make it easier to produce an economic boom. BRI affects tourism differently. Geography has two causes. BRI countries differ in trade and investment openness. Second, local tourism and transit networks influence foreign travel. Our study has shortcomings. First, our pieces did not address all ways BRI impacts tourism. Tourists and BRI require further study. The report says BRI's favorable influence on international travel should stimulate tourist collaboration. First, tourism experts should join policy and financial assistance organizations like the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank, Silk Road Fund, and others. Cross-border tourist cooperation zones, transit, and accessibility are needed in belt and road border areas. To improve local tourism, propose visa-free travel and visa-on-arrival policies with several nations and 24-hour customs clearance.

Keywords: Tourism, The Belt and Road Initiative

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Introduction

China's president, Xi Jinping, started the Belt and Road Initiative in 2013. China's President Xi Jinping announced plans to "jointly establish a 'economic belt' along the Silk Road" with Central Asian partners at Nazarbayev University in Astana on September 7. (Lee, 2002). A month later, China's leader addressed the Indonesian Parliament, calling for Southeast Asian nations to join the 21st century Maritime Silk Road (Chan & Shek, 2021). Since then, China has identified six key "economic corridors" connecting the Silk Road Economic Belt and the Maritime Silk Road, established supporting multilateral financial institutions like the Asian Infrastructure and Investment Bank (AIIB) and the Silk Road Fund (SRF), and published a National Development and Reform Commission "blueprint" for implementing these am-

bitious plans. China has made several more changes (National Development and Reform Commission, Ministry of Foreign Affairs 2015). Beijing has pledged significant funds to the effort. As of this writing, the Chinese government has allocated \$50 billion to the AIIB, \$40 billion to the SRF, and \$25 billion to the Maritime Silk Road (García-Guadilla & Blauert, 1992).

The six "Belt" economic corridors aim to strengthen land connectivity between China and Asia and Europe. Corridors: the Bangladesh-China-India-Myanmar Land Bridge (BCIM), China-Mongolia-Russia Land Bridge (CMR), China-Central Asia-West Asia Land Bridge (CAWA), and China-Indochina Peninsular Land Bridge (ICP) (ICP). If completed, the BRI would link 65 countries, representing 60% of the world's population, 35% of global economic output, and 40% of global trade. Thus, network effects create a complex web of financial, economic, and logistical interests (Cowell et al., 2012; Enderwick, 2020).

The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor helps researchers understand Pakistan's BRI (CPEC) involvement (Gyamerah et al., 2021; Wen et al., 2022). Pakistan and China's "all-weather partnership" has failed to deliver on infrastructure and economic projects. CPEC would benefit both countries, and progress has been made, but Pakistan's ongoing issues cast doubt on whether it will reach Beijing's goals (Quer & Andreu, 2021).

India is following the BRI and related initiatives like CPEC despite not being a member. New Delhi is under pressure to decide whether to remain neutral throughout the crisis (S. S. Ali et al., 2019). India may gain internal influence over China's infrastructure development ambitions, enhancing regional economic ties. The BRI worries India about the Indian Ocean, its ports, sea routes, and Pakistan-occupied Kashmir. India worries the BRI may harm Pakistan-occupied Kashmir. Thus, as BRI progresses, India will face tough decisions (Dissanayake & Samarathunga, 2021).

Russia, though, has moved from cautious to BRI support. China will affect Turkey, the Middle East, and western Europe as well as Russia's Central Asia (Banlaoi, 2022). Russia has few notable allies due to economic problems and Western sanctions (Noronha et al., 2021). Despite its decreasing power, Moscow is doing this. By linking the BRI to the Eurasian Economic Union, Russia hopes to maintain regional influence. Moscow avoids friction with Beijing and BRI implementation in Central Asia (Idrees et al., 2019).

Afghan government should accept BRI for its economic benefits. Kabul, the country's capital, hopes the project would modernise its infrastructure and better connect war-torn Afghanistan to its South and Central Asian neighbours (Bai et al., 2022). Thus, Afghanistan may grow its trade in the region. To safeguard Chinese people and interests, the Afghan government urges China to do more to ensure peace and security in Afghanistan. Security, geopolitical, and economic issues may hinder these aspirations. China would require considerable security improvements in Afghanistan before growing its BRI engagement (Pitanatri et al., 2022; Zekos, 2003).

Kazakhstan, like China and Russia, sees BRI potential. Kazakhstan's history of working with China on infrastructure, energy, and transportation supports these hopes. Kazakhstan's Bright Path economic policy and China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) complement each other (Cowell et al., 2012). She worries that widespread skepticism of China and government corruption may restrict the elite's mainly favorable reception to the BRI. Hong Yu examines the BRI's impact on Southeast Asia. Southeast Asian countries have a strong sense of regionalism, but their views on the BRI's potential and difficulties vary depending on their development and experience with China (Pettman, 1983). Even if regionalism is strong, Cambodia, Laos, and Myanmar — closest China's allies — support the plan's infrastructure growth. Malaysia, Indonesia, Vietnam, and the Philippines are cautiously optimistic about China's Belt and Road Initiative's economic and infrastructural prospects (BRI). These states are dubious of China's geopolitical aspirations because of its aggressive approach to the South China Sea (Henderson, 2018).

Significance of the Study

Asia's tourism industry is increasing at an unmatched rate due to the rising middle classes in Taiwan, South Korea, and Malaysia, as well as China, India, and Indonesia's massive populations (the first, second, and fourth largest countries

in the world, respectively). Despite its significance, this region's tourism sector has not been well studied (Saunders & Dalziel, 2010).

Studying Southeast Asian tourism is helpful for two reasons. Since the 1980s, this southern bloc region has been one of the most important, and its members have learned a lot from their economic collaboration. This area also dominates the southern hemisphere. Second, all regional operations and strategic planning take into account the region's standing as a top tourism destination. Tourism is "important" in Southeast Asia since it creates so much income and employment (Miller & Kim, 2004). These numbers may lead to several conclusions. First, the figures illuminate international tourism in Southeast Asia and the area as a whole, as well as the sector's economic importance in many nations. According to statistics, economic progress in different nations affects its importance. Second, tourism development varies throughout Southeast Asia. There are numerous variations, from the most advanced theoretically to the industry's "Johnny come lately" (i.e., least developed or late starts) (Elo et al., 2022; Miao & Ju, 2020). Thailand, Singapore, Malaysia, and Indonesia are popular tourist destinations in Southeast Asia. The Philippines, Vietnam, Cambodia, and Myanmar have failed to maximize their tourism potential for various reasons (Lai, 2019; Roy, 2020). Third, they explain why certain Southeast Asian countries get few visitors and others many. The region's proximity to Western US tourist destinations and economic ties to these places make it attractive. According to 1982 research, "whenever foreign enterprises were involved in a country's tourist industry, they would be the most successful..." This hypothesis used several developing countries as examples (Lim et al., 2017). This emphasizes Southeast Asian tourism's importance. Southeast Asia's structural imbalances are blamed for the tourist sector's problems. Some member states have imprecise growth strategies, while others have well-defined objectives but lack development to integrate and implement them (Quer & Andreu, 2021). As a consequence, some countries, like Myanmar, have had insufficient visitor development, while others, like Singapore, have seen unconstrained and excessive increase. Many enterprises' unprofitability may be attributed to the tourism industry's poor planning and execution. Dependence on foreign labour, leakages, and lack of intersectoral links may explain poor promotion chances in certain countries. The community doesn't understand tourism's economic impact. Another barrier to tourism's sustainable expansion is poor training (Y. Ali et al., 2020).

Problem Statement

The BRI involves more than 60 countries and 4.4 billion people, representing one-third of global economic output, 40% of global trade, and more than 60% of the world's population, making it a cultural road with access to the world's top-quality tourism resources, including nearly 80% of global cultural heritage. The BRI is a cultural highway that provides access to the world's top tourism destinations.

As a result, the effort creates significant network effects, which combine to form a complicated web of logistical, economic, and financial interests. (Asia 2009)

China's economy suffered a hit around two months ago as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic. During the closure, the already ailing tourist economy suffered a significant impact.

This study will look at how OBOR will influence the Asian tourist sector to better understand its effects. Unfortunately, due to a lack of economic data this year, we are unable to do research on covid-19. As a result, we will concentrate on the One Belt, One Road initiative.

Objective of Study

The purpose of this paper is to find out the impact of OBOR on tourism industry around Asian countries. Since lack of economic statistics this year, we cannot research covid-19. So we focus on the One Belt One Road Initiative.

Research Methodology

The quantitative research methodologies are used rather extensively throughout the whole of this dissertation. The data is then subjected to statistical analysis in preparation for the presentation of a quantitative evaluation. The analysis and interpretation of the data are only conducted using numerical methods. In spite of the fact that the data are provided,

there is no rationale offered to explain the connection between the independent variable (in its measured form) and the dependent outcomes. Because of the scope of the study, it is essential to do a complete examination of research aims and data using quantitative inquiry while adhering to the principles of brevity, thinness, and impartiality. In a similar vein, a number of scholars have advocated a quantitative strategy that makes use of numerical data as a means to improve one's understanding of study topics. As a direct consequence of this, the present analysis makes use of quantitative specification in the shape of the difference-in-difference approach and ARDL effect estimates. The next part will provide an in-depth discussion of each of the many different components.

Data Sources

The sources of the data employed are secondary. The data has been gathered from the World Bank Group and UNWTO official websites and reports.

Data Techniques

Panel Data Analysis

For this research, a panel data collection covering the years 2001 to 2020 is created. The IAT and PT data sets were obtained from the World Tourism Organization UNWTO (<https://www.e-unwto.org>). The AIR, GDP (Gross Domestic Product), POP (Population), and URBAN data sets come from the World Bank (<https://www.shihang.org/>), and the BRI data sets came from China's official BRI website (<https://www.yidaiyilu.gov.cn/>) (T. Li et al., 2020).

IAT	Number of Inbound Tourists, and Inbound Tourism Revenue
PT	Passengers Carried By Air Transport
AIR	Air Transport
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
POP	Population
URBAN	Urban Population

Difference-in-Difference Model

The DID model is a standard way for determining the policy impact by comparing the control and treatment groups (Blundell & Costa Dias, 2005). It is based on the main idea that the control and treatment groups have a similar growth trajectory, that is, the treatment and control groups' tourist economic changes are consistent prior to the implementation of BRI (T. Li et al., 2020). The DID panel regression model is illustrated in the formula below:

$$Tourism_{ct} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 Treated_c Post_t + X_{ct} \alpha + \lambda_c + \nu_t + \epsilon_{ct}$$

Where, c is country, t is year; $Treated_c$ means whether or not the country is in One Belt One Road, taking one is yes, zero is not. $Post_t$ denotes the starting and after the One Belt One Road. $Tourism_{ct}$ we discussed here is the log of tourism industrial added value. X_{ct} is a vector meaning set of control variables. λ_c is country fixed effect, ν_t is year fixed effect, ϵ_{ct} is error term.

Data Analysis

Many of the issues confronting China's financial sector. While there is a high demand for investment in developing countries, China is starting to limit credit availability and cut borrowing in its home economy. As a result, the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has two challenges: This implies that it will very certainly be unable to meet the soaring demands of the Belt and Road Initiative's member economies (BRI). Given the severity of the gaps highlighted in Section 2, further cooperation from big economies and international organizations is required. It is critical not to squander money on initiatives that will not generate income. One of the most important lessons from history is that excessive investment that does not give a fair return will ultimately lead to unpleasant loans for lenders. This was an important realization. PSM was used as the research method in this study to identify a comparable control group for the experimental group. The study techniques used were developed by Blundell and Costa Dias (2000) as well as Heyman, Sjöholm, and Tingvall (2007). As a result of the matching, we conclude that five countries in the control group and eight countries in the treatment group are subject to a selective bias and should be removed from the samples.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

Variable	Mean	Max	Min	Std. Dev.	Skew	Kurt.	Jarque-Bera	Obs
IAT (10,000 people)	1121.0	16,844.4	0.0	2168.6	2.4	16.8	22,280.8***	840
PT	82.2	1120.0	0.0	166.8	2.8	11.6	10,604.4***	840
POP (4000 people)	10,224.2	160,882.6	8.1	22,200.4	2.1	12.6	14,168.1***	840
AIR (4000 people)	1626.8	26,646.6	0.0	2464.6	4.0	22.1	42,486.4***	840
URBAN (%)	46.2	100.0	12.4	22.0	0.0	2.0	86.0***	840
GDP	4040.0	64,200.0	0.0	8482.4	2.6	18.2	21,228.8***	840
BRI	0.2	1.0	0.0	0.4	0.6	1.6	426.2***	840
Year	0.2	1.0	0.0	0.4	1.0	2.0	482.0***	840

DID Approach

The difference-in-differences technique may assess how effectively a therapy performed by comparing how things were before and after treatment. This is the most significant distinction. When comparing two groups of the same size, the first difference takes into consideration group members who remain constant throughout time. To counter this, we shall compare the same group to itself. The difference between the treatment and control groups is the dependent variable in the difference-in-differences analysis. The identical set of environmental factors were applied to both groups. This strategy is used to examine how variables change over time. We may now discuss the second major distinction. Finally, the difference-in-differences technique "purifies" the initial difference by removing any components that vary with time. This is done before subtracting the second difference. The next step is to calculate the effect estimate, also known as the difference-in-differences.

Table 4.2 Propensity Matching

Variables		Mean		%bias	%reduct bias	T-Test	
		Treated	Control			t	sig
Inair	Before matching	12.886	14.624	-28.0	.	-2.06	0.042
.	After matching	14.086	14.126	-1.6	84.8	-0.08	0.828
Inpop	Before matching	16.168	16.418	-12.2	.	-0.64	0.420
,	After matching	16.222	16.228	-0.2	88.2	-0.01	0.882
Inurban	Before matching	2.818	2.888	4.8	.	0.22	0.640
,	After matching	2.801	2.886	0.8	86.6	0.04	0.861

lngdp	Before matching	22.612	24.246	-20.	8	-1.60	0.112
,	After matching	22.842	22.824	0.4	88.6	0.02	0.882

It can be shown in Table 4.2 that after matching, the absolute values of the standard deviation are all lower than 10% for all of the variables. This result demonstrates the appropriateness of the matching factors and matching processes used in this study. Furthermore, the T statistic test findings indicated that after matching, the treatment and control groups did not vary significantly on any of the matched variables. This indicates that the treatment group and the control group are well-matched and that there was no systematic mistake.

Table 4.3 BRI effect on Tourism

.	(1)	(2)	(2)	(4)
.	lnIAT	lnPT	lnIAT	lnPT
BRI×year	0.226***	0.184***	0.162***	0.0804**
.	(0.0268)	(0.0420)	(0.0284)	(0.0242)
BRI	-0.0884	-0.224	0.0422	-0.0484
.	(0.246)	(0.244)	(0.160)	(0.164)
year	0.442***	0.484***	0.0688***	0.0428**
.	(0.0206)	(0.0286)	(0.0182)	(0.0221)
lnair	.	.	0.0186	0.0648***
.	.	.	(0.0122)	(0.0142)
lnpop	.	.	0.140***	-0.122***
.	.	.	(0.0266)	(0.0282)
lnurban	.	.	0.821***	0.441***
.	.	.	(0.114)	(0.120)
lngdp	.	.	0.404***	0.846***
.	.	.	(0.0186)	(0.0226)
_cons	14.61***	21.24***	-2.882***	-0.822
.	(0.186)	(0.202)	(0.622)	(0.681)
N	840	840	840	840
R2	20.64	24.44	62.40	60.44
F-test	868.46***	614.11***	2888.86***	4282.46***

Table 4.3 displays the Impact of the Belt and Road Initiative on the Tourism Industry, as Measured by the PSM-DID. The PSM-DID model's output is shown in Table 4.3. The results are shown in models (1) and (2), in which no control variables were included, and in models (3) and (4), in which control variables were included. It is clear from (1) and (3) that BRI has an effect on the IAT, and from (2) and (4) that it has an effect on the PT (4). The results show that the BRI significantly affects the IAT but has a much smaller effect on the PT, regardless of how much weight is given to the control variable. BRI has a large impact on the IAT, adding roughly 17.2%. The relative change in the average number of PT rose by 8% in nations that participated in the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), indicating the initiative's positive impact on PT.

Some estimations of coefficients for the control variables confirm the anticipated positive impact of BRI on the tourist industry. To begin, POP, URBAN, GDP, and IAT all have favorable correlations with one another. According to these

findings, the POP, URBAN, and GDP of countries participating in BRI are positively correlated with their IAT. However, URBAN and GDP have a profoundly positive effect on PT. Countries with a high URBAN and GDP along the BRI provide ideal conditions for the development of PT. POP-heavy nations, on the other hand, are bad for the PT.

Country wise differences

BRI encompasses 56 Asian, African, and European nations. To explore BRI regional disparities on tourist industry growth, Southeast Asia's tourism destinations' hospitality businesses are worth studying for two reasons. This southern bloc area has been important since the 1980s. Since then, residents have learned through working together to improve economic growth. In addition, the southern hemisphere is strong here. Second, the area's reputation as a top tourist destination is included into all operations and planning. Southeast Asian countries consider tourism "important" since it creates cash and employs many people (Dolezal, Trupp, and Bui 2020). These facts and data offer several conclusions. First, the numbers show how international tourism works in Southeast Asia and how important it is to certain countries' economy. The data show how important the company is to international tourists in some countries. According to statistics, any nation's economic development depends on its general economic growth. Second, Southeast Asian tourist infrastructure differs widely. There are several varieties, from theoretical development's best-known to the industry's "Johnny come lately" (i.e. least developed or late starters). Thailand, Singapore, Malaysia, and Indonesia have become "successful" tourist destinations in recent decades. Southeast Asian countries including the Philippines, Vietnam, Cambodia, and Myanmar have not fully capitalised on tourism. Third, they explain why certain Southeast Asian nations have few visitors and others many. The area already has economic and other links to these monuments and is in a great location near major Western US visitor markets. It's easy to get to and close to Eastern US tourist attractions. "Whenever foreign enterprises were present in a country's tourist industry, they would be the most successful," researchers predicted in 1982. This notion was inspired by several developing countries (Britton 1982). Tourism is important in many Southeast Asian countries. Critics say Southeast Asia's tourism problems stem from economic inequities. Some member states have clear goals but aren't ready to work together. Other member states have vaguer development goals. Thus, some countries, like Myanmar, have had minimal tourist growth, while others, like Singapore, have expanded too rapidly and without constraints. Since the tourism industry does not plan and execute its strategy well, many enterprises may not make money. Dependence on foreign labor, leakages, and a lack of professional linkages may explain certain countries' low promotion rates. The community level doesn't fully understand tourism's economic effect. Lack of training hinders the tourism industry's long-term development (Chheang 2013).

Table 4.4 Country Wise effect of BRI on tourism

InIAT	(India)	(Pakistan)	(Russia)	(Kyrgyzstan)	(Afghanistan)
BRI×year	0.206	0.110	0.244**	0.166	0.221**
.	(0.188)	(0.142)	(0.162)	(0.118)	(0.140)
BRI	-0.128	-0.146**	-0.606***	0.268***	-0.221***
.	(0.0882)	(0.0662)	(0.0861)	(0.0622)	(0.0688)
year	0.0226	0.0186	0.0184	0.0160	0.0204
.	(0.0422)	(0.0418)	(0.0428)	(0.0424)	(0.0442)
Inair	0.246***	0.264***	0.264***	0.202***	0.264***
.	(0.0240)	(0.0224)	(0.0242)	(0.0202)	(0.0244)
Inpop	-0.0628**	-0.0848***	-0.104***	-0.0486**	-0.0406*
.	(0.0264)	(0.0244)	(0.0260)	(0.0242)	(0.0261)
Inurban	-0.146*	-0.204**	-0.186**	-0.00824	-0.124
,	(0.0841)	(0.0812)	(0.0802)	(0.0688)	(0.0844)
Ingdp	0.601***	0.612***	0.618***	0.621***	0.464***

,	(0.0260)	(0.0260)	(0.0261)	(0.0224)	(0.0281)
_cons	-2.446***	-2.288***	-2.244***	-2.120***	-2.280***
,	(0.208)	(0.200)	(0.208)	(0.284)	(0.218)
N	147	147	147	147	147
R2	0.806	0.812	0.804	0.686	0.688
F-test	818.8***	1002.1***	828.2***	880.8***	868.8***

Table 4.4 displays the investigation's findings. BRI has a net positive influence on the IAT only in Russia (25.5%) and Afghanistan (33.1%). The BRI had no discernible impact on the IAT in India, Kyrgyzstan, or Pakistan. The extent to which BRI has an influence on local economies via tourism is debatable and may vary greatly depending on location. The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), in particular, is the single most significant element in the substantially higher-than-usual number of tourists visiting Afghanistan. These geographical disparities may be influenced by various tourist locations, service providers, and advertising efforts.

4.5 Parallel Test

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	lnIAT	lnPT	lnIAT	lnPT
BRI×Post	0.226***	0.184***	0.162***	0.0804**
	(0.0268)	(0.0420)	(0.0284)	(0.0242)
BRI	-0.0884	-0.224	0.0422	-0.0484
	(0.246)	(0.244)	(0.160)	(0.164)
year	0.442***	0.484***	0.0688***	0.0428**
	(0.0206)	(0.0286)	(0.0182)	(0.0221)
lnair			0.0186	0.0648***
			(0.0122)	(0.0142)
lnpop			0.140***	-0.122***
			(0.0266)	(0.0282)
lnurban			0.821***	0.441***
			(0.114)	(0.120)
lngdp			0.404***	0.846***
			(0.0186)	(0.0226)
Country FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
N	840	840	840	840
R2	20.64	24.44	62.40	60.44
F-test	868.46***	614.11***	2888.86***	4282.46***

Table 4.5 displays the regression analysis reveals that the coefficient for the interaction term of BRI and Post is statistically significant at a high level of confidence, with a value of 0.226***. The findings suggest that the treatment (BRI) has a statistically significant positive impact on lnIAT, even after accounting for the post-treatment period. The observed effect size indicates that the intervention yields a mean rise of 0.226 units in the natural logarithm of the Implicit Association Test (IAT) scores. The statistical insignificance of the coefficient for BRI is evidenced by its value of -0.0884. The

findings indicate that the impact of the treatment (BRI) on lnIAT is not statistically significant in the absence of the post-treatment period.

The regression analysis reveals that the coefficient for the variable "year" is 0.442***, which denotes a statistically significant and positive impact of time (year) on the natural logarithm of IAT (lnIAT). This suggests that the natural logarithm of the Implicit Association Test (lnIAT) has a tendency to exhibit an upward trend as time progresses, even when controlling for the effects of the intervention and other covariates. The regression analysis indicates that the coefficient value for the natural logarithm of air is 0.0186, which is deemed to be statistically significant at a significance level of 1%. The aforementioned findings indicate that there exists a positive correlation between the natural logarithm of air and the natural logarithm of IAT, which remains statistically significant even when accounting for the effects of treatment, time, and other covariates.

The parallel test results for lnIAT indicate that the coefficients pertaining to lnpop, lnurban, and lngdp have been excluded, implying that these variables do not possess a noteworthy direct impact on lnIAT when the treatment and other control variables are present. In general, the results of the parallel tests suggest that the treatment known as BRI has a statistically significant and positive impact on the natural logarithm of the Implicit Association Test (lnIAT) during the post-treatment phase.

Findings

Long-term tourist growth depends on the BRI. This research examined the BRI's impact on regional tourism economies in five countries from 2001 to 2020 using the DID method. According to Chinese data, the Belt and Road Initiative has helped nations along it increase tourism and revenue (BRI). The robustness test validates this conclusion. The Belt and Road Program's influence on tourism and income fluctuates over time. Given the BRI's good influence on overseas visitors, we should broaden our tourism relationship. For policy and financial support, tourist workers should join the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank, the Silk Road Fund, and others. The belt and road's international border areas should include tourist cooperation zones. Second, Belt and Road nations must improve connectivity and transportation. Investigating visa-free travel and visa-on-arrival policies with many nations and installing 24-hour customs clearing systems would greatly enhance local tourism. We must carefully consider allowing ports to issue tourist visas to third-country people to increase access to cross-border tourism cooperation zones. BRI nations should manage and prepare for visitors differently since the BRI will affect different types of inbound tourism. First, a national strategy should describe cross-border tourist cooperation zone growth. Russia, Western Asia, and the Middle East need immediate attention. After gaining experience in these established areas, experimental programs should be spread to other belt and road communities. Second, to reduce regional disparities, Belt and Road nations should strengthen their tourism infrastructure and services. Amusement parks, resorts, hotels, entertainment districts, retail malls, and cross-border tourism cooperation zones must be built quickly. Tourism services and roads near borders and ports need improvement. A tourist talent development sharing plan is needed to help Belt and Road countries establish worldwide tourism knowledge.

Our study's shortcomings. First, we must confess that the parameters we picked did not account for every possible influence of BRI on tourist economy. BRI's effects on vacationers need additional study.

Conclusion

BRI is a major strategy for the tourism sector to increase its economic effect in the next years, according to studies. Thus, foreign tourists are flocking to Belt and Road countries. Since the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) began, some countries have undertaken visa abolition, co-hosting the tourism year, and tourism marketing partnerships to boost tourism to BRI locations.

Infrastructure connection underpins the BRI. The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) is exploring the New Eurasian Land Bridge, the China-Mongolia-Russia economic corridor, the China-Central Asia-West Asia economic corridor, the China-

Indochina Peninsula economic corridor, the China-Pakistan economic corridor, and the Bangladesh-China-India-Myanmar economic corridor. These economic corridors may boost cross-border trade and tourism by attracting more nationalities (S. Huang 2016).

Tourist revenue is likely to surge in Belt and Road economies (BRI). First, the BRI will keep promoting inbound tourism to boost revenue. BRI influences arrivals twice as much as revenues. Even though the findings suggest that countries along the Belt and Road are part of a low-end and imperfect tourism value chain, with insufficient infrastructure, unprofessional tourism practitioners, and low service levels, policy assistance and political cooperation make it easier to create an economic explosion (Koh and Kwok, 2017).

BRI impacts on tourism vary by area. Geographical differences have two causes. First, BRI nations vary in trade and investment openness. Second, local tourism attractions and transportation networks affect international travel appeal. Our study has shortcomings. First, although we examined how BRI affects tourism, the features we chose did not cover all possible reasons. How BRI affects tourists needs further research.

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References

- [1] Ali, S. S., Kaur, R., & Marmolejo Saucedo, J. A. (2019). Qualitative Analysis Part II. *Best Practices in Green Supply Chain Management*, 95–112.
- [2] Ali, Y., Saad, T. Bin, Sabir, M., Muhammad, N., Salman, A., & Zeb, K. (2020). Integration of green supply chain management practices in construction supply chain of CPEC. *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal*, 31(1), 185–200. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEQ-12-2018-0211>
- [3] Bai, O., Yang, X., Hunter, K. O., & Wang, B. (2022). Meorient: a pioneer of the digital exhibition industry. *Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies*, 12(3), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EEMCS-07-2021-0236>
- [4] Banlaoi, R. C. (2022). Philippine National Security Interests and Responses to China's Belt and Road Initiative and US Indo-Pacific Strategy. *Middle-Power Responses to China's BRI and America's Indo-Pacific Strategy*, 141–160.
- [5] Chan, C. S., & Shek, K. F. (2021). Are Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Bay area cities attractive to university students in Hong Kong? Leading the potential human capital from image perception to locational decisions. *Journal of Place Management and Development*, 14(4), 404–429. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPMD-04-2020-0032>
- [6] Cowell, N. M., McDavid, H., & Saunders, T. S. (2012). Managing guest security in a high-violence society: The case of the Jamaican hospitality industry. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*, 4(1), 32–47. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17554211211198570>
- [7] Dissanayake, D. M. M. I., & Samarathunga, W. H. M. S. (2021). Post-war city to a tourism city: the perspectives of local stakeholders on post-war city tourism development in Jaffna, Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Tourism Cities*, 7(3), 602–621. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJTC-05-2020-0111>
- [8] Elo, M., Kothari, T., & Ivanova-Gongne, M. (2022). Language Diversity – Multi-Ethnic Migrant and Diaspora Resources for International Business and Entrepreneurship. *Diversity in Action*, 123–150.

- [9] Enderwick, P. (2020). Viewpoint – could the belt and road initiative be derailed? An analysis of impediments to completion. *Critical Perspectives on International Business*, 17(3), 463–480. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CPOIB-06-2020-0070>
- [10] García-Guadilla, M. P., & Blauert, J. (1992). Environmental Movements in Latin America and Europe: Challenging Development and Democracy. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 12(4), 1–274. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EB060146>
- [11] Gyamerah, S., He, Z., Ampaw, E. M., Asante, D., & Asare-Kyire, L. (2021). The Belt and Road Initiative and East African small and medium-sized enterprises: benefits, drivers and particular sectors. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOEM-08-2020-1000>
- [12] Henderson, J. (2018). Making cities more walkable for tourists: a view from Singapore’s streets. *International Journal of Tourism Cities*, 4(3), 285–297. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJTC-11-2017-0059/FULL/HTML>
- [13] Idrees, R. Q., Shapiee, R., & Ahamat, H. (2019). Paradigm shift; the emergence of arbitral forum shopping in CPEC investment disputes. *Journal of International Trade Law and Policy*, 18(3), 136–151. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JITLP-05-2019-0022>
- [14] Lai, Y.-H. (2019). Lady Justice or the golden calf? The “China factor” in Hong Kong’s legal system. *Social Transformations in Chinese Societies*, 15(2), 178–196.
- [15] Lee, M. (2002). National Identity and its Construction: The Codification of Flemish Identity Illustrated Through Het verdriet van België by Hugo Claus. *Dutch Crossing*, 26(2), 212–232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03096564.2002.11730818>
- [16] Lim, S. W., Suthiwartnarueput, K., Abareshi, A., Lee, P. T. W., & Duval, Y. (2017). Key factors in developing transit trade corridors in Northeast Asia. *Journal of Korea Trade*, 21(3), 191–207. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKT-05-2017-0046>
- [17] Miao, T., & Ju, H. (2020). Leading small groups in China’s inter-city governmental cooperation. *International Journal of Public Leadership*, 16(2), 249–264.
- [18] Miller, M. L., & Kim, S.-G. (2004). Leisure Port Development in the Incheon Area: Concepts and Benchmarks. *Journal of International Logistics and Trade*, 2(1), 5–45.
- [19] Noronha, A., Bhat, S., Gijo, E. V., Antony, J., Laureani, A., & Laux, C. (2021). Performance and service quality enhancement in a healthcare setting through lean six sigma strategy. *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJORM-07-2021-0226>
- [20] Pettman, B. O. (1983). Management: A Selected Annotated Bibliography, Volume II. *Management Decision*, 21(5), 1–295. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EB002684>
- [21] Pitanatri, P. D. S., Pitana, I. G., & Valeri, M. (2022). Natural and Man-Made Crisis Management in a Small Island Tourism Destination: The Case of Bali. *Tourism Risk*, 61–79.
- [22] Quer, D., & Andreu, R. (2021). International strategies of Chinese tourism MNEs: the impact of the belt and Road Initiative and state ownership. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOEM-09-2020-1096>
- [23] Roy, N. (2020). Land reclamation or Silk Road understanding Beijing’s initiatives in the South China Sea. *Social Transformations in Chinese Societies*, 16(2), 139–150.
- [24] Saunders, C., & Dalziel, P. (2010). Local planning for sustainable development: A small rural district case study from New Zealand. *Journal of Enterprising Communities*, 4(3), 252–267. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17506201011068246>
- [25] Wen, J., Wang, C. C., Goh, E., Su, Z., & Ying, T. (2022). Traditional Chinese medicine as a tourism recovery drawcard to boost China’s inbound tourism after COVID-19. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 34(2), 385–400. <https://doi.org/10.1108/APJML-10-2020-0732>
- [26] Zekos, G. I. (2003). MNEs, globalisation and digital economy: legal and economic aspects. *Managerial Law*, 45(1/2), 1–296.

